

Self-Acceptance of Deaf Students in an inclusive environment at SLB Negeri 1 Padang

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to explore the self-acceptance of deaf students in an inclusive environment at SLB Negeri 1 Padang. Using a qualitative approach, the study involves in-depth interviews with students, teachers, and direct observation in the classroom to understand the factors that affect the self-acceptance of deaf students. The results showed that social support from teachers and peers, inclusive teaching methods, and active participation in extracurricular activities contributed significantly to student self-acceptance. However, deaf students still face challenges in communication and social interaction, which affects their confidence and the way they see themselves. This research provides important insights for educators and stakeholders in designing better educational strategies to support the self-acceptance of deaf students in an inclusive environment. Thus, the results of this study are expected to be a reference for a more inclusive and friendly education policy for all students.

KEYWORDS: Admissions, Students, Deaf, Inclusive Environments, Schools

INTRODUCTION

Everyone has a basic need to communicate and interact with the people around them. Social interaction shapes a person's personality, identity, and social and emotional skills. Social interaction is very important in the growth and development of children, including children with disabilities such as the deaf. Social interactions that occur between students at school, especially in Special Schools (SLB), affect their cognitive, emotional, and social development. and the need for social interaction is the same as that of a child with normal hearing. In the (Supena & Iskandar, 2021) explained that Children with Special Needs (ABK) are individuals who have lost or experienced a decrease in sensory function that has an impact on learning problems or behavioral problems, and who have intellectual privileges so that they need special education services to develop their potential that is still and already hasi.(2)

Inclusive education is an approach that integrates students with special needs, such as deaf students, into the same learning environment as students without special needs. In Indonesia, the implementation of inclusive education is very important to increase access to education for all children, as well as to build a more equitable and inclusive society. SLB Negeri 1 Padang is one of the educational institutions that is committed to providing a friendly learning environment for deaf students and other students.

Self-acceptance is an important process that affects how deaf students see themselves and interact with their social environment. Self-acceptance is closely related to students' psychological aspects, such as self-esteem, self-confidence, and the ability to adapt to a new social environment. Deaf students often face problems in communication and social interaction, which can affect their self-acceptance. Research conducted by Rohmah et al shows that parenting style is proven to be one of the factors for self-acceptance of deaf children. In addition, there are several other factors such as school, teachers, friends and parents.

Deaf students have the same cognitive abilities to learn, communicate, and participate in social activities at school, even if they are deaf. That's why it's important to see deaf students as individuals who have the same needs and abilities as other students, even if their communication styles differ.

Research conducted by (Antia & Stinson, 2002) shows that deaf students experience various barriers in social interaction with peers, especially when in an environment that does not support inclusive communication. (4) The psychosocial development of deaf students is highly dependent on their need to be accepted, recognized, and feel equal to their peers. However, communication difficulties often lead to social isolation, feelings of inferiority, and limitations in building strong relationships with peers.

The inclusive environment at SLB Negeri 1 Padang aims to create an atmosphere where every student feels welcome and valued. However, there are still problems, especially in communication and social interaction. Therefore, this study aims to examine the self-acceptance of deaf students in the inclusive environment of SLB Negeri 1 Padang. This research will focus on the factors that affect their self-acceptance. It is hoped that this research will provide in-depth insight into the social dynamics that occur in the

school environment and how this affects the self-acceptance of deaf students. This will be done through direct observation and interviews with students and teachers.

CONCEPTUAL

1. INCLUSIVE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT.

Deaf students are people with hearing impairments that interfere with their ability to hear and understand sounds, which can be complete (deaf) or partial (hard of hearing). (5)Defining deaf children are children with hearing loss who are classified as deaf and hard of hearing. This is stated in Law No. 8 of 2016 concerning Persons with Disabilities that it is explained that Persons with Disabilities are any person who experiences physical, intellectual, mental, and/or sensory limitations for a long period of time who in interacting with the environment can experience obstacles and difficulties to participate fully and effectively with other citizens based on equal rights(6). The same thing is explained (Hernawati, 2007)Deaf children are children who experience disorders in their hearing organs that result in hearing impairment, ranging from mild to very severe which are classified into deaf and hard of hearing.

In Special Schools (SLB), deaf students are categorized as part of children with special needs (ABK) who have impaired hearing. Based on the Regulation of the Minister of National Education (Permendiknas) No. 70 of 2009 concerning Inclusive Education, deaf people are included in the category of sensory disabilities which include impaired hearing function and/or impaired speech function.(7)

A special educational approach is necessary for deaf students because they often have difficulty receiving and processing auditory information. To overcome their limitations, deaf students often receive specialized learning services in private schools that emphasize the use of sign language, lip reading, or total communication (a combination of sign and speech) to communicate. In addition, the curriculum and learning approach at SLB need to be adapted to communication skills and the needs of deaf people..

Deaf students often need assistive devices such as sign language or hearing aids, or alternative communication methods, to communicate and participate in learning activities. In research, it is said that deaf children are children who have hearing impairments so that they cannot hear sounds perfectly or even cannot hear at all, but it is believed that there is no human being who cannot hear at all. They have the same intellectual and social abilities as other students but need additional assistance to be able to participate fully in the school environment.

The condition of a person's inability to hear something, either in total or in part, can be called deafness. (Gunawan, 2016) says that a deaf person is a person who has a hearing impairment usually at a level of 70 deciBeli (dB) or more so that it will have difficulty being able to understand or understand what others are saying.(5)

Table. 2.1 (Christine, 2016) (5)

Table with 3 columns: No, dB, Keterangan. It lists hearing levels from 0 dB to above 91 dB and their corresponding descriptions.

No dB 1 0 dB Shows optimal hearing 2 0-26 dB Still has normal hearing 3 27-40 dB Difficulty hearing distant sounds 4 41-55 dB Requires hearing aids and speech therapy 5 6 56-70 dB Classified as moderately severe deafness 71-90 dB Severe deafness 7 Above 91 dB Above is classified as very severe deafness (Christine, 2016)

2. INCLUSIVE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT.

Inclusive education is one way to overcome social problems for children with disabilities. It is an educational model that offers students with special needs the opportunity to learn together with students their age who do not have special

needs. Inclusive education in Permendiknas No. 70 of 2009 is defined as an education delivery system that provides opportunities for all students with disabilities and have the potential for intelligence or special talents to participate in education or learning in an educational environment together with students in general. (8)

An inclusive educational environment is an educational system that aims to ensure that all students enjoy equal opportunities regardless of their physical, cognitive, social, or sensory limitations. Dalam (8,9) explained that Inclusive Education is an effort by the government to provide education equally in fulfilling the right to education for all children, by including children with special needs in regular schools.

Inclusive education entails what is required for deaf students. This includes providing hearing aids, sign language interpreters, or recording instructions on how to communicate with suppliers and other deaf people. Inclusive education is a form of educational service that integrates the learning of children with special needs (ABK) with children in general in order to participate and obtain educational services with systems, methodologies, and learning that are in accordance with their needs and abilities (Abosi & Koay, 2008) in the (10)

Research by (4) demonstrate that an inclusive environment can improve social interaction and academic development of deaf students. If deaf students have an environment at school that supports two-way communication, they may feel more welcome at school, participate in group activities, and interact with their peers. In SLBs, where deaf students are placed alongside students with other special needs, it is important to ensure that the school environment is actually helpful in interacting.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses a qualitative descriptive method with a case study approach to analyze the self-acceptance of deaf students in the inclusive environment of SLB Negeri 1 Padang. This method was chosen because it is in accordance with the purpose of the research which wants to describe in depth the process of self-acceptance of deaf students and the factors that influence it in the context of an inclusive school. This research focuses on direct observation, interviews, and documentation as the main data collection techniques.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The self-acceptance of deaf students in an inclusive environment at SLB Negeri 1 Padang is an important aspect that affects their psychological and social development. The results show that several key factors contribute to the self-acceptance of deaf students.

I. Social Support.

The self-acceptance process for deaf students relies heavily on social support from teachers and their peers. Students feel welcome in a group because of positive social interactions, such as sharing experiences and learning together. Having support from the people around deaf students really helps them adapt as they often have difficulty communicating. This is in line with research that shows that peer social support can affect deaf students in high school inclusion schools by 85.2% ($R = 0.852$).

An interview with one of the teachers, Mrs. Andrianita, a teacher of SLB Negeri 1 Padang, revealed, "The approach is various, from giving support, being hugged, being taken for a walk and when it is calm then she can interact with her" Therefore, it shows that support from teachers is very important in building the self-acceptance of deaf students at SLB Negeri 1 Padang.

Students who receive emotional support from teachers, both verbally and nonverbally, tend to feel more welcome in the school environment. Teachers at SLB Negeri 1 Padang actively pay special attention to deaf students, both through direct communication such as eye contact, sign language, and interactions that motivate students to participate in classroom activities. Previous research has shown that teacher support is one of the main factors influencing the self-acceptance of children with special needs, especially the deaf. Teachers who provide attention and personalized guidance help deaf students feel valued and accepted, despite their physical limitations.

II. Supportive Environment

Another important factor in increasing the self-acceptance of deaf students is an inclusive environment. Their efforts to make SLB Negeri 1 Padang a friendly and fun place for all students helps reduce the stigma that deaf students often experience.

Deaf students can interact without feeling left out because of school policies that emphasize equality and understanding of differences.

The teacher of SLB Negeri 1 Padang, Mrs. Sandra as a teacher of SLB Negeri 1 Padang, explained, "At school we always make students comfortable with the existing environment such as we mention the word "hello" while waving or being kind with a touch to students so that students feel comfortable and feel supported. A supportive environment provides a foundation for students to develop confidence and accept themselves as they are.

III. Application of Varied Learning Methods.

Different teaching methods greatly affect the self-acceptance of deaf students. Verbal and nonverbal communication, such as body language and sign language, helps students better understand the lesson. As said by Mrs. Adrianita as a teacher of SLB Negeri 1 Padang, revealed that "in the teaching and learning process of deaf students, we go through various methods ranging from learning methods in the surrounding environment, and learning methods in the classroom using platforms so that students feel comfortable and easy to understand."

Teachers can adapt their teaching methods to the needs of the deaf so that they do not feel left behind..

The self-acceptance of deaf students at SLB Negeri 1 Padang is greatly influenced by social support, a supportive environment, various learning methods, and their participation in extracurricular activities. Schools have an important role to play in creating an environment that supports the admission of deaf students. The study shows that by considering these elements, schools can help deaf students develop best academically and socially..

According to the theory of symbolic interactionism, a person's meaning is shaped by their social interactions. This theory is consistent with the findings of this study. Deaf students form their identity and self-esteem in such contexts through their relationships with others in school.

1. Emotional Support as an Important Factor: Teachers and peers can help deaf people feel welcome. If students feel supported, they will be better able to cope with problems and actively participate in school activities.
2. Social Interaction and Self-Acceptance: Positive social interaction increases self-acceptance. Extracurricular activities help deaf people interact with others. In addition, it increases feelings of attachment and community.
3. Difficult to Communicate The main obstacle for deaf students is limited communication. This shows that non-deaf students need to be educated and made aware so that they can better understand and interact with their deaf friends.
4. Positive Self-Perception Deaf students' social experiences are closely related to their self-acceptance. Students can gain more confidence and receive consistent support from the school environment. It can also help them accept themselves..

CONCLUSION

According to this study, many factors affect the self-acceptance of deaf students in an inclusive environment at SLB Negeri 1 Padang. These factors include social support, interaction with peers, and teachers' teaching methods. The main findings of this study are:

1. Significant Social Support: Deaf students who receive emotional and social support from their teachers and peers tend to be more accepting of themselves. With this support, students feel more valued and accepted in the school community.
2. The Role of Social Interaction: Deaf students increase their self-esteem by interacting positively with their peers. Students who actively participate in activities inside and outside the classroom have a more positive attitude towards themselves.
3. Challenges: Despite the many positive aspects, deaf students face difficulties when communicating and interacting with others. Often, communication difficulties lead to feelings of isolation, which can hinder the process of self-acceptance.
4. Recommendations for School Environments: Schools should implement a more inclusive approach to teaching and improve non-deaf students' knowledge of what their peers need. In addition, teachers need to be trained in effective communication techniques to create a more supportive environment for students with hearing loss..

Overall, the study emphasizes that an inclusive school environment and social support are essential for improving the acceptance of deaf students. This impacts their social and emotional development, as well as their academic achievement and involvement in the school community.

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